

Learning-Based Computation-Aware Access-Point Clustering and Joint Radio-Compute Allocation in Dynamic Cell-Free MEC Networks

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Abstract—User-centric cell-free massive MIMO is a key 6G technology to meet strict latency and energy-efficiency demands of compute-intensive applications. In practical O-RAN deployments, the central unit and distributed unit compute capacity fluctuates with network-slicing dynamics. Relying on fixed compute resources and access-point (AP) clustering based solely on radio conditions leads to radio-compute mismatches, which in turn create bottlenecks that degrade both latency and energy efficiency. To address this drawback, we propose a communication and computation-aware AP-clustering strategy with joint resource allocation, leveraging a multi-agent reinforcement learning framework. The learned policies reduce average device energy consumption by 45% versus a fixed-compute RL benchmark and by 70% versus an offloading-first FPC heuristic across 10–50 Mbit/s, while maintaining 98–100% deadline satisfaction.

Index Terms—Cell-free massive MIMO, Multi-agent reinforcement learning, Mobile edge computing, 6G networks, Energy efficiency, O-RAN

I. INTRODUCTION

THE past decade has seen a surge of latency-critical and compute-intensive services that challenge conventional mobile edge computing (MEC). In response, user-centric cell-free (CF) massive multiple-input multiple-output (mMIMO) has emerged as a beyond-5G/6G paradigm, where distributed access points (APs) jointly serve each user equipment (UE) without cell boundaries [1]. Coupled with edge computing, the resulting CF-MEC fabric provides reliable connectivity with uniform coverage, enabling strict 6G services to meet tight deadlines while reducing device energy [2], [3].

As computation is offloaded from UEs to the edge to reduce device-side processing energy, secure and efficient fronthaul and backhaul transport becomes critical, motivating ongoing interest in quantum key distribution secured transport for supporting dynamic and sensitive traffic flows [4]–[6].

Despite this promise, practical CF-MEC deployments, particularly within the Open RAN (O-RAN) architecture, face a key challenge stemming from dynamically shared and time-varying edge compute resources [7]. Under network slicing and closed-loop RAN Intelligence Controller (RIC) operation,

the server CPU budget—defined here as the total edge processing capacity available at the Centralized Unit (O-CU) and its associated Distributed Units (O-DUs) fluctuates with slice load, admission decisions, and service mix [8], [9].

Much of the CF-MEC literature assumes fixed or abundant edge compute capacity and forms AP clusters solely from physical metrics such as large-scale fading or distance. Neglecting these CPU constraints creates CPU-side bottlenecks and a radio-compute mismatch that increases end-to-end delay and energy under aggressive offloading. Conversely, compute-centric policies that ignore rate under-utilize the radio access.

In this work, we propose a Joint Radio-Compute Clustering and Resource Allocation (JRCC-RA) framework for a user-centric CF-MEC uplink, where the CPU compute budget is modeled as time-varying. Each UE jointly controls its transmit power to shape rate and radio energy, its local CPU factor to trade energy for delay, and the number of serving APs. By adapting AP clustering to both radio conditions and instantaneous CPU availability, the offloading load is aligned with CPU capacity. The problem is formulated as a sequential decision process using lightweight local observations, enabling real-time continuous control without centralized optimization.

The proposed framework extends the CF-MEC paradigm with a compute-aware and continuous JRCC-RA design based on a centralized training with decentralized execution (CTDE) multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) approach. The main contributions are summarized as follows:

- Dynamic-compute CF-MEC model. We explicitly capture slice-driven, time-varying server CPU with proportional sharing among offloaded tasks, exposing the radio-compute coupling in end-to-end latency and energy. The model also accounts for dynamic traffic arrivals consistent with realistic 6G service demands.
- Compute aware AP clustering with joint control. We extend radio only clustering by incorporating both communication and computation states, enabling coordinated control of transmit power, local CPU, and cluster size.

TABLE I: Summary of important notations.

Notation	Description
M, K	Number of APs and UEs
W	System bandwidth
τ_c, τ_p	Coherence block length and pilot length
C^{\max}	Maximum AP cluster size
$N_k(t)$	Serving APs for UE $_k$ at time t
g_{mk}	Channel from AP $_m$ to UE $_k$
β_{mk}	Large scale fading coefficient
h_{mk}	Small scale fading with $h_{mk} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$
$\mathcal{T}_k(t)$	Task size in bits arriving at UE $_k$ at time t
$t_k^d(t)$	Task deadline of UE $_k$ at time t
N_{cpb}	CPU cycles per bit
ς	Switched capacitance coefficient
f_k^{\max}	Maximum local CPU frequency
$\alpha_k(t)$	Local CPU factor with $f_k^{\text{local}}(t) = \alpha_k(t)f_k^{\max}$
p_k^{\max}	Maximum transmit power
$\eta_k(t)$	Power factor with $p_k(t) = \eta_k(t)p_k^{\max}$
$\gamma_k(t)$	Continuous selector mapped to $N_k(t)$ via (10)
$f(t)^{\text{CPU}}$	time-varying server CPU budget at the O-CU and O-DU pool
$f_k^{\text{CPU}}(t)$	Server CPU share allocated to UE $_k$ at time t
ξ_k	Penalty factor for missed deadlines in (11)

Fig. 2: Illustrative system model: Cell-Free Massive MIMO-enabled mobile edge network.

area (Fig. 2). A single O-CU design avoids inter O-CU synchronization and message passing, reducing control latency and stabilizing MARL training via a centralized critic and coherent network-wide updates [18].

The uplink channel from AP $_m$ to UE $_k$ is $g_{mk} = \sqrt{\beta_{mk}} h_{mk}$, where β_{mk} captures large-scale effects and $h_{mk} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ denotes the small-scale fading coefficient. Each coherence block of τ_c symbols reserves τ_p pilots and $\tau_c - \tau_p$ data symbols. Each UE $_k$ is served by $N_k(t) \leq C^{\max}$ APs, selected as those with the largest β_{mk} . Uplink detection uses maximum-ratio (MR) combining over the signals received at the $N_k(t)$ serving APs. The resulting signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) follows the standard CF mMIMO MR-combining expression for user-centric serving, and the achievable uplink rate is

$$R_k(t) = W \left(1 - \frac{\tau_p}{\tau_c} \right) \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_k(t)), \quad (1)$$

where W is the system bandwidth.

At the beginning of time step t , UE $_k$ receives a task of $\mathcal{T}_k(t)$ bits, split into local and offloaded parts: $\mathcal{T}_k(t) = \mathcal{T}_k^{\text{local}}(t) + \mathcal{T}_k^{\text{offload}}(t)$. The processing density is N_{cpb} CPU cycles/bit and the switched-capacitance coefficient is ς . The local CPU runs at $f_k^{\text{local}}(t) = \alpha_k(t)f_k^{\max}$ with $\alpha_k(t) \in [0, 1]$. Given the per-UE deadline $t_k^d(t)$, the executed local task size, delay, and energy are:

$$\mathcal{T}_k^{\text{local}}(t) = \min \left\{ \mathcal{T}_k(t), \frac{t_k^d(t) f_k^{\text{local}}(t)}{N_{cpb}} \right\}, \quad (2a)$$

$$t_k^{\text{local}}(t) = \min \left\{ \frac{\mathcal{T}_k^{\text{local}}(t) N_{cpb}}{f_k^{\text{local}}(t)}, t_k^d(t) \right\}, \quad (2b)$$

$$E_k^{\text{local}}(t) = \varsigma \mathcal{T}_k^{\text{local}}(t) N_{cpb} (f_k^{\text{local}}(t))^2. \quad (2c)$$

The remaining task is offloaded:

$$\mathcal{T}_k^{\text{offload}}(t) = \max \{ 0, \mathcal{T}_k(t) - \mathcal{T}_k^{\text{local}}(t) \}. \quad (3)$$

With $p_k(t) = \eta_k(t)p_k^{\max}$, the uplink transmission delay and energy can be compactly expressed as:

$$t_k^{\text{tr}}(t) = \frac{\mathcal{T}_k^{\text{offload}}(t)}{R_k(t)}, \quad E_k^{\text{offload}}(t) = p_k(t) t_k^{\text{tr}}(t). \quad (4)$$

To capture slicing dynamics, the server CPU budget $f(t)^{\text{CPU}}$ is time-varying and shared proportionally to the instantaneous offloaded demand:

$$f_k^{\text{CPU}}(t) = \frac{\mathcal{T}_k^{\text{offload}}(t)}{\sum_{j=1}^K \mathcal{T}_j^{\text{offload}}(t)} f^{\text{CPU}}(t), \quad (5a)$$

$$t_k^{\text{comp}}(t) = \frac{\mathcal{T}_k^{\text{offload}}(t) N_{cpb}}{f_k^{\text{CPU}}(t)}. \quad (5b)$$

Furthermore, the end-to-end delay is determined as:

$$t_k(t) = \max \{ t_k^{\text{local}}(t), t_k^{\text{tr}}(t) + t_k^{\text{comp}}(t) \}, \quad (6)$$

while the total energy consumption is determined as the sum of local and offloaded components:

$$E_k(t) = E_k^{\text{local}}(t) + E_k^{\text{offload}}(t). \quad (7)$$

Our objective is to minimize the total energy consumption $\sum_{k=1}^K E_k(t)$ subject to per-UE deadlines, following established CF-MEC formulations [10].

V. MULTI-AGENT RL-BASED DISTRIBUTED JRCC-RA

We adopt a CTDE scheme with one agent per UE; the overall architecture is shown in Fig. 3.

A. Problem and DRL Formulation

Each UE is an agent. At time t , agent k observes

$$o_k(t) = [\mathcal{T}_k(t), f(t)^{\text{CPU}}, R_k(t-1)], \quad (8)$$

and outputs the continuous action

$$a_k(t) = [\eta_k(t), \alpha_k(t), \gamma_k(t)], \quad (9)$$

where $\eta_k(t) \in [0, 1]$ sets the transmit power $p_k(t) = \eta_k(t)p_k^{\max}$, and $\alpha_k(t) \in [0, 1]$ sets the local CPU $f_k^{\text{local}}(t) = \alpha_k(t)f_k^{\max}$. The third component $\gamma_k(t) \in [0, 1]$ is a continuous

Fig. 3: Centralized training, decentralized execution architecture for distributed JRCC-RA.

cluster-size selector, mapped at execution to an integer number of serving APs as

$$N_k(t) = 1 + \text{round}((C^{\max} - 1)\gamma_k(t)). \quad (10)$$

UE_k is then served by the $N_k(t)$ APs with the largest β_{mk} . These blocks correspond to “Joint Observation” and “Joint Action” in Fig. 3.

We define the reward as the negative of the total system energy consumption across all UEs, and all agents receive the same shared reward $r_k(t)$:

$$r_k(t) = - \sum_{k=1}^K \xi_k E_k(t). \quad (11)$$

The coefficient ξ_k is a deadline-aware weight. It is set to $\xi_k = 1$ when UE_k meets its latency constraint and to $\xi_k = 10$ otherwise, which increases the penalty for late tasks. This design rewards energy efficiency only under timely execution and strongly discourages deadline violations. During training, the centralized critic observes the joint state $s(t)$ and joint action $a(t)$, while execution remains fully decentralized using only local observations.

B. MADDPG for JRCC-RA

We adopt a MADDPG-style CTDE framework [19], where each UE acts as an agent whose actor maps local observations to the action triple $\mathbf{a}_k(t) = [\eta_k(t), \alpha_k(t), \gamma_k(t)]$. A centralized critic, used only during training, observes all agent’s states and actions to mitigate non-stationarity and improve credit assignment.

Training proceeds with experience tuples stored in a replay buffer. Mini-batches are sampled to update the critic via temporal difference (TD) learning and the actors via deterministic policy gradients. Target networks with soft updates ensure stability, and Gaussian noise is added for exploration. Features (task size \mathcal{T}_k , CU budget f^{CPU} , rate proxy R_k) are normalized, and rewards are scaled for consistency.

The centralized critic leverages global information to learn policies that offload more when CU compute is abundant and shift to local processing when it is scarce, while jointly

coordinating radio choices $(\eta_k(t), \gamma_k(t))$. After training, only the decentralized actors run at the UEs, requiring solely local inputs $[\mathcal{T}_k(t), f(t)^{\text{CPU}}, R_k(t-1)]$ without global signaling or extra fronthaul. Offline training uses fixed seeds, synchronized target updates, and standard MADDPG hyperparameters [19]. Here, $f(t)^{\text{CPU}}$ is time-varying due to slice-level network control; although it may remain constant over several coherence blocks in practice, we treat it as varying at each decision step as a worst-case model, so that each UE can use an available CPU-capacity estimate (e.g., broadcast by the RIC/O-CU) during decentralized execution.

VI. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This section presents the simulation setup and discusses the numerical results for JRCC-RA.

A. Simulation Setup

We consider a user-centric CF-MEC uplink with $M=100$ single-antenna APs and $K \in \{5, 10, 15\}$ UEs uniformly distributed over a $1000 \times 1000 \text{ m}^2$ area. We use carrier frequency $f = 1.9 \text{ GHz}$, AP height $h_{\text{AP}} = 15 \text{ m}$, and UE height $h_{\text{UE}} = 1.65 \text{ m}$. Each UE is served by the APs with the strongest large-scale fading coefficients. For heuristic benchmark algorithms, a fixed cluster size of $N_k(t) = 0.3M = 30$ APs is used, while in the proposed JRCC-RA framework the cluster size is dynamically adapted. Unless stated otherwise, the system parameters include bandwidth $W=5 \text{ MHz}$, coherence block $\tau_c=100$ symbols with $\tau_p=K$ pilots, noise temperature $T=290 \text{ K}$ with $\text{NF} = 9 \text{ dB}$, peak UE power $p_k^{\max}=0.1 \text{ W}$, maximum local CPU $f_k^{\max}=1 \text{ GHz}$, switched-capacitance constant $\varsigma=10^{-27}$, and $N_{\text{cpt}}=500$ cycles/bit. Path loss follows a multi-slope model with log-normal shadowing (std. 10 dB) and Rayleigh small-scale fading. At each time step t , tasks arrive i.i.d. with $\mathcal{T}_k(t) \in [2.5, 7.5] \text{ kbit}$ and per-UE deadlines $t_k^d=1 \text{ ms}$. The server CPU budget (O-CU/O-DU pool) is dynamic, $f(t)^{\text{CPU}} \sim \mathcal{U}[10, 100] \text{ GHz}$ (the benchmark uses a fixed 100 GHz), and offloaded bits share server CPU cycles proportionally.

The agents use the observation and action definitions in Section V, including the mapping in (10). Actor and critic are MLPs with hidden layers [128, 64, 64] (ReLU), with Sigmoid actor outputs. We use replay capacity 10^5 , batch size 128, discount factor 0.99, soft target update $\tau = 0.005$, learning rates 10^{-4} (actor) and 10^{-3} (critic), and Gaussian exploration with variance annealed to ≈ 0.05 . Training runs for 200 episodes with 25 steps per episode, and features are normalized.

As a heuristic reference, we adopt the offloading-first policy with fractional power control (FPC) [20], where all tasks are offloaded and the uplink power is set as

$$p_k(t) = \min(p_k^{\max}, p_0 \lambda_k(t)^{-\nu}), \quad (12)$$

with p_0 in linear Watts ($p_0 = -35 \text{ dBm}$), $\nu = 0.5$, and $\lambda_k(t)$ the aggregated large-scale fading over the $N_k(t)$ serving APs (i.e., the sum of the $N_k(t)$ largest β_{mk} values for UE_k). We also benchmark against the MADDPG-based joint allocation framework of [10], but under the simplified assumption of a

Fig. 4: Episodic reward for MDDPG in the CF-MEC setup with $K = 10$ UEs. Thin gray: raw per-episode values; blue: moving average (window=10).

Fig. 5: Total energy consumption per episode for MDDPG in the CF-MEC setup with $K = 10$ UEs. Thin gray: raw per-episode values; blue: moving average (window=10).

fixed CU capacity of 100 GHz, representing a widely used yet optimistic setting that disregards dynamic compute variability.

B. Results and Discussion

We report (i) the episodic reward, (ii) the total energy consumption per episode (J), (iii) the success rate (deadline satisfaction), and (iv) the offload ratio.

Fig. 4 shows a rapid rise and subsequent stabilization of the episodic return, indicating that the MDDPG effectively learns energy-efficient, deadline-feasible operating points under a time-varying server CPU budget. This aligns with Fig. 5, where total energy consumption drops sharply in the early episodes and continues to decline steadily. The results demonstrate that the learned policy not only optimizes the intended cost but also adapts by selecting appropriate AP clusters and transmit power levels, thereby reducing overall energy consumption.

Reliability remains high throughout training (Fig. 6), with deadline satisfaction around 98% – 100%. Fig. 7 illustrates adaptive offloading: the offload ratio increases and then tracks the available compute $f(t)^{\text{CPU}}$ —more cycles lead to more offloading (smaller $\alpha_k(t)$), while scarcity shifts work locally.

Fig. 8 provides a scalability comparison of MDDPG in the CF-MEC setup, for various numbers of UEs. As Fig. 8 indicates, slower convergence and lower steady-state rewards

Fig. 6: Task success rate (deadline satisfaction) over training for MDDPG in the CF-MEC setup with $K = 10$ UEs. Thin gray: raw per-episode values; blue: moving average (window=10).

Fig. 7: Offloading ratio over training for MDDPG in the CF-MEC setup with $K = 10$ UEs. Thin gray: raw per-episode values; blue: moving average (window=10).

Fig. 8: Scalability comparison of MDDPG in the CF-MEC setup with $K \in \{5, 10, 15\}$ UEs. Blue squares: $K = 5$; orange circles: $K = 10$; green triangles: $K = 15$. All curves are moving averages with window=10 (no raw traces).

as K grows from 5 to 15 due to higher contention, yet training remains stable across all sizes.

Fig. 9 summarizes the energy–throughput tradeoff. The proposed policy is the most energy-efficient across 10–50 Mbit/s. At 20 Mbit/s, it consumes 0.15 J versus 0.60 J (proposed benchmark) and 0.80 J (offloading-first (FPC)), i.e., $\approx 75\%$ and $\approx 81\%$ lower energy, respectively; at 50 Mbit/s, it uses 1.30 J versus 1.80 J and 4.00 J, i.e., $\approx 28\%$ and $\approx 68\%$

Fig. 9: Energy–throughput tradeoff in the CF–MEC setup comparing the proposed MADDPG, a benchmark policy, and an offloading–first (FPC) heuristic.

lower energy. These gains stem from jointly observing the instantaneous CPU capacity $f(t)^{\text{CPU}}$ and adjusting cluster size $\gamma_k(t)$, transmit power $\eta_k(t)$, and local CPU share $\alpha_k(t)$, which enables offloading when resources are abundant, local execution when the edge is congested, and rate boosting only when the energy–delay tradeoff is favorable, thereby reducing wasteful transmissions and improving energy efficiency.

While JRCC-RA captures radio–compute coupling under time-varying CU capacity, several simplifications remain. We assume a single CU (no inter-CU coordination/load balancing) and model CU scheduling via proportional compute sharing, without explicit queueing or priority effects. We also omit fronthaul latency and control–signaling overheads. Finally, scalability to larger UE/AP deployments will be assessed in extended studies.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper addressed JRCC-RA in user-centric CF–MEC networks with dynamic CU capacities, motivated by O-RAN slicing. We proposed a compute-aware framework where each UE jointly optimizes transmit power, local CPU frequency, and cluster size using a CTDE MADDPG scheme. Simulation results with up to 15 UEs and 100 APs showed consistent energy reductions while preserving near-perfect reliability. On average, the method achieved 45% energy savings over a fixed-compute benchmark and 70% over an offloading–first FPC heuristic, all while maintaining 98–100% deadline satisfaction. These results confirm the benefit of coupling compute-awareness with clustering and joint radio–compute control. Future research will extend the framework to multi-CU topologies with inter-CU cooperation and explore multi-slice scenarios with heterogeneous QoS demands.

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